

Statistical Optimization for Ethanol Production by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) Using Response Surface Methodology

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Received: January 8, 2015, Accepted: February 11, 2015, Published: February 11, 2015.

ABSTRACT

Response surface methodology based on central composite design was applied to optimize the fermentation conditions of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) for maximum ethanol recovery. The influence of process parameters were investigated by design expert software, optimum conditions were found to be pH of 3.5, temperature of 35°C and initial sugar concentration of 4% glucose. By optimizing with coded factor the maximum ethanol production observed by the model was 10.5 g/l ethanol. This design proved to be optimization of culture conditions and increase the ethanol productivity.

Keyword: *S. cerevisiae*, RSM, CCD, Ethanol production, Optimization

INTRODUCTION

On account of limited global supply of oil, ethanol has emerged as an alternative for petroleum based liquid fuels. It is used in automobiles as an alternative fuel has attracted worldwide attention for its production on a large scale while maintaining the economic status of a country. Biofuel production process; whether biogas, bioethanol or biodiesel are entirely different and unique. Through the processes of transesterification, fermentation or anaerobic digestion, biofuels are created from organic material and refined, for use in vehicles or in other applications. In present state of energy crises, efforts are being made to reduce the dependence upon nonrenewable energy sources, one of which is fuel alcohol produced by fermentation of agricultural or agro industrial wastes and byproducts. An efficient ethanol production requires four components: fermentable carbohydrates, an efficient yeast strain, a few nutrients and simple culture conditions. Approximately 80% of world supply of alcohol is produced by fermentation of sugar and starch containing crops or byproducts from industries based on such crops^[1].

Yeasts are most often used in the fermentation process and obtain energy from various carbon sources. Yeasts are the most common microorganisms for ethanol fermentation. Among the yeast kingdom, *S. cerevisiae* is one of the well known ethanol producers. Ethanol is an essential chemical which is used as a raw material for a vast range of applications including chemicals, fuel (bioethanol), beverages, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics. *S. cerevisiae* has short germination time and is easily cultured in large scale processes^[2].

The traditional method for optimization of parameters involves optimizing one parameter at a time. This is not only a time-consuming process, but often misses the alternative effects between components. Limitations of one-at-a-time-parameter

optimization can be eliminated by employing Response surface method (RSM) which is used to explain the combined factors in a fermentation process^[3]. Generally, RSM defines the effect of the independent process variables, alone or in combinations, and generates a mathematical model that describes the entire process. Also, the RSM summarizes mathematical methods and statistical inference for an approximate functional relationship between a response variable and a set of design variables. The most popular RSM is the Central composite design (CCD) which is an efficient and flexible technique that provides sufficient information on the effects of process variables and overall experimental error with a minimum number of experiments^[4].

In the purpose of present work, response surface methodology was used to optimize the culture conditions of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) for maximizes the ethanol productivity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Yeast strain

Saccharomyces cerevisiae (MTCC 170) was procured from Microbial Type Culture Collection, Chandigarh, India. The culture was maintained on YEPD agar slants at 4°C for further studies. In the previous studies, the optimization of culture conditions of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) for ethanol production was carried out at traditional method. The various parameters studied such as initial sugar concentration (1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6%), pH (2.5 to pH 5.5), temperature (25, 30, 35 and 40°C) within this multiple variables screen the highest ethanol producing factors was selected as central point and used in central composite design (CCD) of response surface methodology (RSM).

Experimental design and statistical analysis

Response surface methodology was used to optimize the culture conditions for the ethanol production by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170). Central composite design was used consisting of three factors at two level patterns showed in the Table.1. pH, temperature and glucose were taken for optimization by a rotatable central composite design (CCD) resulting in 20 experimental runs. The treatment combinations were allocated into block [5]. The first block contained the factorial runs accompanied by four central runs. The second block contained the axial runs accompanied by two central runs. The modeling and statistical analysis analyses were performed using Design Expert, version 8.0.4.1 software (Stat-Ease Inc. Minneapolis).

Fermentation Process

All experiments were carried out in 250 ml Erlenmeyer flasks with working volume of 100 ml. A 24 hrs cell suspension of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* MTCC 170 was inoculated into 100 ml of fermentation medium containing: yeast extract-1g; peptone-1g. For experimental designs, 20 runs were carried out with different conditions of pH, incubation temperature and initial sugar concentration used showed in the Table.2. The fermentation process was carried out for 48 hrs with agitation rate 200 rpm. After incubation to estimate the amount of ethanol was present in the each flask.

Estimation of ethanol by potassium dichromate and sulphuric acid method

Ethanol assay from sample was tested by the method of Caputic [6]. Culture supernatant (1ml) was taken and make up the volume to 5ml with distilled water then followed by 1ml of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution and 4ml of Conc. H_2SO_4 solution was added. The intensity of colour was read at 660nm in UV/VIS spectrophotometer (Systronics, 119). Ethanol production was assayed by comparing with standard graph.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Statistical Optimization for Ethanol Production by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) Using Response Surface Methodology

Ethanol production by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) was optimized using CCD and RSM. The quadric model was used in the version of design expert 8.0.4.1 software. Ethanol production was optimized by varying concentration of the medium components especially glucose (carbon source) and the two factors (pH and temperature). The optimization of condition was performed using CCD with fixed central points of pH 3.5, temperature 35°C and glucose 4%.

RSM helps evaluation of relationship between dependent (ethanol production) variable and independent variable (media components and factors like pH, temperature) observed values of the ethanol production as shown in the Table 2.

The co-efficient and analysis of variance are presented in the Table 3. The model F – value (8.48) and p – value (0.05) implies the model terms were significant. There is only a 0.13% chance that a “Model F-Value” this large could occur due to noise. Values of “probe >F-value” less than 0.0500 indicates model terms are significant. In this case C, BC, A^2 , B^2 , C^2 are significant model terms. Values greater than 0.1000 indicate the model terms are not significant. The fit of the model was checked by the co-efficient of determination R^2 was calculated to be 0.8842 indicating that 11.58% of variability in the response could be explained in the model.

Regression Equation for the level of ethanol production in terms of coded factor

$$Y1=+10.49+0.17*A-0.14*B+0.38*C-0.25*A*B+0.40*A*C+0.65*B*C-0.61*A^2-0.66*B^2+0.96*C^2\dots(1)$$

By optimizing in the Equation (1) the following conditions were obtained the maximum ethanol production predicted by the model was 10.5 g/l. Response surface and contour plot figures obtained by the analysis of the experimental data of CCD showed a relationship between two variables at time while maintaining third variables at a constant level. These figures are helpful in understanding both linear and interaction effect of two variables. The 3-D response surface plot (RS) described by the regression model were drawn to illustrate the combined effects of the independent variables and combined effects of each independent variables upon the response variable.

In Fig. 3, the response surface plots illustrating the effect of the temperature and glucose keeping pH at constant level (pH-3.5). The plot revealed that the ethanol production was low at lower limit and increasing temperature resulted in an increasing ethanol production where as increasing glucose concentration less production of ethanol.

The data observed by the varying concentration of glucose and different pH at constant temperature (35°C) was plotted in Fig. 2. It shows that on initial increase in pH with simultaneous increase in glucose concentration resulted in an increase ethanol production. However on increase beyond this limit has affected the ethanol production.

The interaction of pH-3.5 and temperature (35°C) with the fixed coded values of glucose (4%) an increasing pH with simultaneous increase in temperature let to an initial increase in ethanol production until they reached the optimal ethanol production was showed in the response surface plot Fig. 3.

RSM analysis for ethanol production

Response surface methodology is one of the scientific approaches that is useful for developing, improving and optimizing processes and is used to analyze the effects of several independent variables on the system response, main objective being the determination of optimum operational parameters within the operating specifications [7]. This method has been successfully applied to optimize alcoholic fermentation process [8].

In the present study response surface methodology used to optimize the culture conditions for ethanol production by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170). Central composite design was used for three variables at two level patterns. pH, temperature and glucose were taken for optimization by a rotatable central composite design (CCD) resulting in 20 experimental runs for optimum ethanol production. The maximum ethanol production (10.5 g/l) was obtained in this experiment using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) in optimum conditions were such as: pH-3.5, temperature-35°C and glucose 4%. Similar results were reported by Hoda et al [9] *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (PTCC 24860) growth on pretreated sugar beet molasses was an optimized via statistical approach with the application of a central composite design (CCD) under response surface methodology (RSM). The optimal culture conditions were pH of 5.3, incubation time of 24 h and medium composition of 35 g reduced sugars, 1.5 g NH_4Cl and 1 g yeast extract per liter of the media. At optimal cell growth conditions and incubation time of 12 h, the maximum ethanol production of 14.87 g/L was obtained by this model.

Similar results were reported by Karuppaiya et al ^[10] the central composite designs (CCD) involving the variables substrate composition (20-100%), pH (4.5-6.5), incubation temperature (28-36°C) and fermentation time (12-160 hrs), in response surface methodology optimize the production of ethanol from waste cashew apple juice by *Zymomonas mobilis* MTCC 090 was obtained maximum ethanol concentration (12.64 g/l). Sasikumar and Viruthagiri ^[11] reported that using RSM parameters setup for reaching a maximum response for ethanol production was obtained when applying the optimum values were temperature (32°C), pH (5.6) and fermentation time (110 hrs). Maximum ethanol concentration (3.36 g/l) was obtained from 50 g/l pretreated sugarcane bagasse at the optimized process conditions in aerobic batch fermentation by cellulase and *Pachysolen tannophilus* MTCC 1077.

Central composite design used to optimize the culture conditions of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) for ethanol production. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) produce higher amount of ethanol. This experimental design increases the ethanol production than traditional method of optimization. Similar results were reported by Palukurty et al ^[12] ethanol production using jaggery was enhanced in submerged fermentation when the effect of metal inducers was studied using the Central composite design.

Saccharomyces cerevisiae (NCIM 3288) was used as the fermenting organism. The Central composite design was used to initially screen seven of which the four elements were found to have significant effect on ethanol production. It was observed that ethanol yield has increased to 94.8 from 75.4 g/l when supplemented with the critical concentrations of salts provided by the model.

Table 1. Independent variables and their coded levels for the central composite design used in the present study for ethanol production by *S. cerevisiae* (MTCC 170)

VARIABLES	CODED VARIABLE LEVELS		
	-1	0	1
Glucose (%)	3	4	5
Temperature (°C)	30	35	40
pH	3	3.5	4

Table 2. Central composite experimental Fraction factorial design for ethanol production by *S. cerevisiae* (MTCC 170)

RUN	FACTOR:A GLUCOSE (%)	FACTOR: B TEMPERATURE (°C)	FACTOR:C PH	RESPONSE:1 ETHANOL (g/L)
1	5	30	3	9.6
2	4	35	3.5	10.5
3	5	40	4	10
4	4	26.59	3.5	8.8
5	4	35	3.5	10.5
6	3	30	4	7.5
7	5.68	35	3.5	8.6
8	4	35	3.5	10.5
9	4	43.41	3.5	8
10	5	40	3	6.7
11	4	35	4.34	8.8
12	4	35	3.5	10.5
13	4	35	3.5	10.5
14	2.32	35	3.5	8.5
15	3	40	3	8.4
16	5	30	4	8.4
17	3	40	4	8.2
18	4	35	2.66	6.3
19	3	30	3	8.4
20	4	35	3.5	10.5

Table 3. ANOVA for Ethanol production by *S. cerevisiae* (MTCC 170)

Terms	<i>S. cerevisiae</i> (MTCC 170)
F Value	8.48
P>F	0.05
Mean	8.96
R ²	0.8842
Adjusted R ²	0.7799
Co-efficient variance %	6.89
Adequate precision	8.91

Fig. 1. Three-dimensional response surface plot for the effects of sugar concentration and incubation temperature on ethanol production by *S. cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) at a constant pH.

Fig. 2. Three-dimensional response surface plot for the effects of sugar concentration and pH on ethanol production by *S. cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) at a constant incubation temperature.

Fig. 3. Three-dimensional response surface plot for the effects of incubation temperature and pH on ethanol production by *S. cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) at a constant sugar concentration.

CONCLUSIONS

Using RSM based on CCD model, Optimum conditions for ethanol production by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) were: pH-3.5, temperature-35°C and glucose 4%. By optimizing with coded factor the maximum ethanol production observed by the model was 10.5 g/l of ethanol. Conventional methods of optimization for ethanol production are extremely time-consuming and expensive. In Response surface methodology is efficient in easy to handling large number of design parameters and maximize the ethanol yield, reduce the cost of production.

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Citation: K. T. K. Anandapandian, et al. (2015). Statistical Optimization for Ethanol Production by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170) Using Response Surface Methodology. *J. of Advancement in Medical and Life Sciences*. V2I3. DOI: 10.15297/JALS.V2I3.04

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